

Evaluating the Combined Effects of Aspartame and Acesulfame Potassium on Reproductive Hormones, Liver Function, and Oxidative Stress in Female Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

The use of combinations of artificial sweeteners, particularly, acesulfame potassium (E950) and aspartame (E951), in foods, beverages, and other products is increasing, despite different reported side effects. This study investigated the effects of acesulfame potassium and aspartame, individually and in combination on reproductive hormones, liver function, and oxidative stress markers in female Wistar rats. Twenty-five female rats (90.7 ± 8.1 g) were divided into five groups, A-E. Group A (the control) received distilled water, group B received a combination of 15 mg/kg acesulfame potassium and 50 mg/kg aspartame, group C received acesulfame potassium (15 mg/kg body weight), group D received aspartame (50 mg/kg body weight), and group E received sucrose (330 mg/kg body weight) for twenty-eight days. The oral combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame decreased the serum concentrations of progesterone (2.0 ± 0.60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), estradiol (15.70 ± 0.60 pg/mL), and follicle-stimulating hormone (6.50 ± 0.30 mIU/mL), when compared with control (4.50 ± 0.15 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, 28.20 ± 1.50 pg/mL , and 9.80 ± 0.40 mIU/mL respectively) with a corresponding increase in serum AST. Although antioxidant enzyme activities were not altered, reduced glutathione levels increased in the combination group (1.10 ± 0.05 mmol/L) compared with 1.10 ± 0.03 mmol/L in control. Sucrose-treated rats exhibited no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) from the control group. At the tolerable daily intake levels (15 mg/kg body weight and 50 mg/kg body weight, respectively), a combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame interfered with the ovarian hormonal level and imposed stress on the liver's redox profile. It may not be completely safe for consumption. Therefore, this suggests the need for caution in consuming artificial sweetener combinations and calls for further studies to elucidate their long-term effects on health.

Keywords: Acesulfame Potassium, Aspartame, Cellular Biomarkers, Reproductive Hormones.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial sweeteners, sometimes known as "sugar substitutes" or "non-nutritive sweeteners," are typically calorie-free or low-calorie chemical additives that are used to sweeten meals and beverages instead of sugar (Das and Chakraborty, 2018). Since the flavors of the various artificial sweeteners differ in strength, duration, aftertaste, solubility, and durability at different pH levels and temperatures, they are combined to boost sweetness (Souza *et al.*, 2022).

Acesulfame potassium (acesulfame-K) and aspartame are 200 times sweeter than sucrose (Klug *et al.*, 2012). Acesulfame-K is widely used in sweetener blends and in conjunction with bulk sweeteners like aspartame in products that require high stability, such as confectionery or bakery goods, and soft drinks, because of its synergistic qualities (Serrano and Riebl, 2019). Aspartame contains 4 calories per gram and it

is catabolized in the small intestine by esterases and peptidases to aspartic acid, phenylalanine, and methanol (Kroger *et al.*, 2006).

Concerns regarding the dependability and security of several diet-related products, particularly the use of low-calorie sweeteners, are growing among consumers. New information indicates that artificial sweeteners could be harmful to human health (Wang *et al.*, 2018). The usage of artificial sweeteners, particularly those found in soft drinks, has been linked to lipid buildup, fibrosis, and liver deterioration (Al-Hadrawy, 2022). Artificial sweeteners have been associated with issues with the reproductive system such as polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and anovulation in a later age (Bridge-Comer *et al.*, 2021).

Ingestion of sweeteners in processed meals may be associated with health issues, for example; methylene

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chloride, a known carcinogen, is included in acesulfame-K may harm the liver, kidneys, brain, and cancer (Helal *et al.*, 2019). In addition, type 2 diabetes, preterm birth, nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, and the production of histological abnormalities in the parotid salivary glands are all risks associated with aspartame use (Bekheet, 2020). Despite the side effects reported for using each of aspartame and acesulfame potassium, these two are continuously found in foods and drinks like carbonated drinks, beverages, cereals, and sugar-free sweets. The combination of these two sweeteners would most likely result in increased side effects. There is limited information on the safety and risks of combined aspartame and acesulfame-K use on reproductive hormones and liver antioxidant profiles. So, this study aims to bridge the gap of insufficient information on the safety of the combination of aspartame and acesulfame-K on female rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Solvents

Aspartame and Acesulfame-K were products of Vitasweet®, Co., Ltd. Shanghai, China. Alkaline phosphatase (ALP), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), bilirubin, albumin, total protein, glutathione reductase, and glutathione peroxidase were products of Fortress Diagnostic Limited United Kingdom. Progesterone, estrogen, follicle-stimulating hormone, and luteinizing hormone were products of Calbiotech Inc. USA. Epinephrine, and adenosine triphosphate salts were products of Sigma-Aldrich Company, reduced glutathione was a product of Santa-Cruz Biotechnology Company, 5'5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB) and 1-chlorodinitrobenzene (CDNB) and all other chemicals and reagents used were supplied by Sigma –Aldrich Inc. (St. Louis, MO).

Experimental Animals

Twenty-five female Wistar rats (90.70 ± 8.10 g) were obtained from the animal section of the Department of Biochemistry, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria. All the rats were kept in plastic cages in a well-ventilated animal house. They were allowed free access to feed and tap water and handled strictly according to the instructions in the Guidelines on Care and Use of Laboratory Animals.

Preparation of Chemicals

Acesulfame potassium and aspartame were prepared in distilled water to yield 15 and 50 mg/kg body weight, respectively. The combination was prepared by merely mixing the prepared solutions. Sucrose was prepared to give a dose of 330 mg/kg body weight using distilled water.

Animal grouping and treatments

Twenty-five female rats were housed in a cage and allowed to acclimatize for 1 week before the experiment. The animals were randomly assigned into five groups of four rats and treated as follows:

Group 1: received 0.5 mL of distilled water,

Group 2: received 0.5 mL of combined aspartame and acesulfame-K which correspond to 50 mg/kg body weight (b.w) respectively.

Group 3: received 0.5 mL of acesulfame-K corresponding to 15 mg/kg b.w.

Group 4: received 0.5 mL of aspartame corresponding to 50 mg/kg b.w.

Group 5: received 0.5 mL of sucrose corresponding to 330 mg/kg b.w.

The doses were administered orally once daily for 28 days, with the aid of a plastic oropharyngeal cannula.

Preparation of Serum and Tissue Supernatants

The procedure described by Yakubu *et al.* (2009) and Ajiboye *et al.* (2014) was adopted for the preparation of serum and tissue supernatants. Twenty-four hours after the 28-day administration of the distilled water, aspartame, and acesulfame-K, the rats were weighed and anesthetized in diethyl ether fumes. Following the loss of consciousness, the jugular veins were cut, and 3 ml of blood was collected into plain and heparin sample bottles. Clear serum was then collected using a Pasteur pipette after centrifuging the clotted blood samples at $1252 \times g$ for 10 minutes using Biobase Laboratory Centrifuge (Model LC- 4KA, Jinan, China). The sera were kept frozen for 12 hours before further analysis. The animals were then quickly dissected, and the liver and kidneys were carefully removed and blotted. The organs were weighed and placed in an iced cold 0.25 M sucrose solution to maintain the integrity of the tissues. The organs were separately homogenized after which they were centrifuged at $1789 \times g$ for 10 minutes. The supernatants were frozen for 12 hours before the assessment of some biochemical parameters.

Female reproductive hormone assays

Progesterone, estrogen, follicle-stimulating hormone, and luteinizing hormone in the serum were determined using the procedure outlined in commercial kits (Calbiotech Inc, USA).

Biochemical Examinations

Various biochemical parameters were assessed in the serum and tissue homogenates. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) were determined using the method described by Reitman and Frankel (1957). Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels were measured using the method established by Roy (1970), and bilirubin levels were

determined as in Jendrassik and Grof (1938) method. Albumin levels were determined as outlined by Rodkey (1965). Total protein concentration was measured using the Weichselbaum (1946) method.

Furthermore, the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) was determined following the procedure described by Misra and Fridovich (1972), while Catalase (CAT), glutathione reductase (GSH), and malondialdehyde (MDA) activity were determined following the procedures of Beers and Sizer (1952), Sedlak and Lindsay (1958), and Pilz *et al.* (2000) respectively. Protein carbonyl concentration was also determined according to the procedure described by Levine *et al.* (1990).

Data Analysis

The data obtained from five replicated measurements were used to calculate the mean and standard error of the mean. In addition, a one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the statistical difference with a significance level at $p < 0.05$ using GraphPad Prism version 6.01 software (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, California, United States).

RESULTS

Concentration of female reproductive hormones

Following the oral administration of a combination of acesulfame-K and aspartame, sucrose, aspartame, and acesulfame-K, no significant ($p > 0.05$) difference was observed in the concentration of luteinizing hormone compared to the control (Figure 1). The serum concentrations of progesterone in rats exposed to the combination of acesulfame-K and aspartame were significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased when compared to the control group. It is noteworthy to know that no statistical ($p > 0.05$) difference was observed following the administration of only aspartame at 50 mg/kg b.w when compared with the control. Similarly, administration of sucrose at 330 mg/kg b.w compared well with the control group showing no significant increase or decrease in the level of progesterone. However, administration of only acesulfame-K at 15 mg/kg b.w shows a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the level of progesterone when compared with the control (Figure 2).

A significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the concentration of follicle-stimulating hormone was observed following the oral administration of acesulfame-k, aspartame, and the combination of both acesulfame-K and aspartame, while a significant increase after oral administration of sucrose at 330 mg/kg b.w. was noted (Figure 3) with the concentration of estradiol of rats exposed to acesulfame-K, aspartame and the combination of both significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased when compared to the control group while the sucrose administered at 330 mg/kg b.w. compared well with the control group (Figure 4).

Biochemical Indices

The specific activities of superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione transferase, and glutathione peroxidase in rats exposed to the different groups that received acesulfame-K, aspartame, and the combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame, as well sucrose were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) changed when compared to the control rats (Table 1). The concentrations of protein carbonyl and malondialdehyde were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) altered. The concentration of reduced glutathione shows a significant difference in rats that received the combination of aspartame and acesulfame-k, 15mg/kg b.wt acesulfame-k, and 330mg/kg b.wt sucrose when compared with control. It should be noted that no significant difference was observed in rats that received 50mg/kg B.wt aspartame when compared with the control (Table 2).

Total protein, albumin, direct, and total bilirubin concentration in the liver of rats exposed to the acesulfame-k, aspartate, sucrose, and the combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) altered when compared to the control rats (Table 3). Also, the specific activities of alanine aminotransferase and alkaline phosphatase in the liver and serum of rats exposed to the combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame were not significantly ($p > 0.05$) changed when compared to the control rats. However, the specific activity of aspartate aminotransferase in the liver and serum of rats exposed to the combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame were significantly ($p < 0.05$) altered when compared to the control rats (Table 4).

Figure 1: Serum concentration of luteinizing hormone of female rats exposed to acesulfame-K, aspartame, sucrose, and the combination of both acesulfame-K and aspartame

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same

group are not significantly different at $p > 0.05$. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $p < 0.05$.

Figure 2: Serum concentration of progesterone of female rats exposed to acesulfame-K, aspartame, sucrose, and the combination of both acesulfame-K and aspartame

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same

group are not significantly different at $p > 0.05$. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3: Serum concentration of follicle stimulating hormone of female rats exposed to acesulfame-K, aspartame, sucrose, and the combination of both acesulfame-K and aspartame. Values are mean \pm

S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same group are not significantly different at $p>0.05$. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $p<0.05$.

Figure 4: Serum concentration of estradiol of female rats exposed to acesulfame-K, aspartame, sucrose, and the combination of both acesulfame-K and aspartame. Values are mean \pm S.E.M of five replicates. The means

having the same superscript within the same group are not significantly different at $p>0.05$. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $p<0.05$.

Table 1: Specific activities of enzymic antioxidant indices in female rats exposed to a combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame different superscript in the same column are significantly different $p < 0.05$.

Parameters (mmol/L/min/mg protein)	Control	Aspartame+Acesulfame-k	Acesulfame-k (15mg/kg b.wt)	Aspartame (50mg/kgbwt)	Sucrose (330mg/kg bwt)
Superoxide Dismutase	1.60 ± 0.04 ^a	1.50 ± 0.06 ^a	1.40 ± 0.05 ^a	1.50 ± 0.07 ^a	1.40 ± 0.01 ^a
Catalase	6.10 ± 0.14 ^a	5.00 ± 0.23 ^a	4.20 ± 0.16 ^b	6.60 ± 0.51 ^a	5.40 ± 0.29 ^a
Glutathione Transferase	0.37 ± 0.02 ^a	0.36 ± 0.02 ^a	0.37 ± 0.02 ^a	0.43 ± 0.01 ^a	0.41 ± 0.01 ^a
Glutathione Peroxidase	26.00 ± 0.51 ^a	27.00 ± 1.40 ^a	24.00 ± 0.55 ^a	24.00 ± 0.4 ^a	25.00 ± 0.80 ^a

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The mean having same superscript within the same column are not significantly different at $p > 0.05$. Mean with

Table 2: Concentration of non-enzymic antioxidant indices in female rats exposed to a combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame

Parameters (mmol/L/min/mg protein)	Control	Aspartame+Acesulfame-k	Acesulfame-k (15mg/kg B.wt)	Aspartame (50mg/kgB.wt)	Sucrose (330mg/kgB.wt)
Reduced Glutathione	0.79 ± 0.03 ^c	1.10. ± 0.05 ^b	1.80 ± 0.04 ^a	0.95 ± 0.19 ^c	1.30 ± 0.06 ^a
Protein Carbonyl	1.40 ± 0.06 ^a	1.30 ± 0.03 ^a	1.40 ± 0.11 ^a	1.20 ± 0.07 ^a	1.20 ± 0.09 ^a
Malondialdehyde	5.30 ± 0.09 ^a	5.60 ± 0.15 ^a	5.40 ± 0.21 ^a	5.50 ± 0.17 ^a	5.50 ± 0.12 ^a

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same column are not significantly different at $p > 0.05$. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different $p < 0.05$.

Table 3: Concentration of liver function parameters in female rats exposed to a combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame

Parameters (mg/dL)	Control	Aspartame+ Acesulfame-k	15mg/kg B.wt Acesulfame-k	50mg/kg B.wt Aspartame	330mg/kg B.wt Sucrose
Liver Protein	59.00±2.36 ^a	58.66±2.79 ^a	60.71±2.22 ^a	59.09±0.47 ^a	62.42± 0.63 ^a
Serum Protein	31.88±1.29 ^a	33.33± 0.68 ^a	29.15± 0.64 ^a	31.96±0.86 ^a	30.67±1.19 ^a
Albumin	10.19±0.54 ^a	10.02±0.59 ^a	10.01±0.31 ^a	11.23±0.32 ^a	10.47±0.74 ^a
Direct bilirubin	27.36±1.84 ^a	33.18±2.31 ^a	29.82±1.19 ^a	25.68±1.75 ^a	27.48±2.22 ^a
Total bilirubin	25.68±1.75 ^a	25.42±1.70 ^a	25.60±1.65 ^a	25.48±1.64 ^a	25.62±1.83 ^a

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same column are not significantly different at p>0.05. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different p<0.05.

Table 4: Specific activities of cellular marker enzymes in female rats exposed to a combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame

Parameters (U/I/mg)	Control	Aspartame+ Acesulfame-k	15mg/kg B.wt Acesulfame-k	50mg/kg B.wt Aspartame	330mg/kg B.wt Sucrose
ALP Liver	10.73 ± 0.54 ^a	10.36 ± 0.51 ^a	10.22 ± 0.52 ^a	10.29±0.63 ^a	10.05±0.54 ^a
Serum ALP	7.29 ± 0.40 ^a	7.50 ± 0.30 ^a	8.16 ± 0.20 ^a	7.57± 0.38 ^a	7.89± 0.36 ^a
AST Liver	118.60 ± 2.34 ^d	69.19 ± 6.94 ^e	237.60 ±12.43 ^a	136.60±12.75 ^b	122.40±5.90 ^c
Serum AST	76.94 ± 2.27 ^c	110.4 ± 4.73 ^a	111.40±4.73 ^a	89.99± 4.58 ^b	89.61±3.45 ^b
ALT Liver	80.10 ± 4.21 ^a	79.95 ± 4.13 ^a	82.29±4.69 ^a	82.74±4.91 ^a	79.88± 4.15 ^a
Serum ALT	18.08 ± 1.41 ^a	18.85 ± 0.41 ^a	25.23± 0.87 ^b	21.97± 1.11 ^a	21.77± 0.98 ^a

Values are mean ± S.E.M of five replicates. The means having the same superscript within the same column are not significantly different at p>0.05. Mean with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different p<0.05.

Discussion

Artificial sweeteners (sugar substitutes or non-nutritive sweeteners), are calorie-free or low-calorie chemical additives used to sweeten meals and beverages instead of sugar (Das and Chakraborty, 2018). This study investigates how acesulfame potassium, aspartame, and their combination affect reproductive hormones, liver function parameters, and oxidative stress markers in female Wistar rats.

Reproductive hormones such as progesterone, estradiol (a form of estrogen), follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), and luteinizing hormone (LH) play pivotal roles in the female reproductive system. Progesterone is essential for maintaining pregnancy and regulating the menstrual cycle, estradiol supports follicular development and secondary sexual characteristics, FSH stimulates ovarian follicle maturation, and LH triggers ovulation. The combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame significantly reduced progesterone, estradiol, and FSH levels, while not affecting LH. The reduction in progesterone and estradiol could impair ovarian function, leading to irregular cycles or infertility. Similar hormonal disruptions have been linked to artificial sweeteners in previous studies, where altered estrogen and progesterone levels were associated with reproductive dysfunction (Serrano and Riebl, 2019).

Furthermore, the observed decrease in FSH could alter follicular maturation, potentially leading to conditions such as anovulation, as reported by Bridge-Comer *et al.* (2021). Interestingly, sucrose-treated rats maintained normal hormonal levels, indicating no adverse effects on reproductive function. This suggests the relative safety of natural sugars at recommended doses, contrasting with the endocrine-disrupting effects of artificial sweeteners.

The liver is central to metabolism and detoxification, and its function can be assessed through parameters such as total protein, albumin, bilirubin, and liver enzymes like alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST). These enzymes are markers of hepatocyte integrity and metabolic activity, with elevated serum levels often indicating liver damage or stress. While albumin, total protein, and bilirubin levels remained stable across all groups, liver AST activity significantly decreased, with a corresponding increase in serum AST in rats treated with the sweetener combination. This suggests hepatocyte damage or membrane leakage. Similar findings have been reported by Al-Hadrawy (2022), who linked artificial sweeteners to hepatotoxic effects.

The lack of significant changes in ALT levels observed in this study suggests limited direct hepatocellular damage. However, the increased serum AST implies potential mitochondrial stress or liver membrane permeability alterations, potentially caused by sweetener metabolites such as methanol (from aspartame) and diketopiperazine (Kroger *et al.*, 2006).

Oxidative stress plays a critical role in cellular damage, with enzymatic antioxidants like superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, glutathione transferase, and glutathione peroxidase, along with non-enzymatic antioxidants like reduced glutathione, forming the primary defense system. Malondialdehyde (MDA) and protein carbonyl levels indicate lipid peroxidation and protein oxidation, respectively, and elevated levels suggest oxidative damage. The enzymatic antioxidant activities and levels of MDA and protein carbonyl remained unchanged across all groups, indicating no severe oxidative stress. However, reduced glutathione levels increased significantly in groups treated with acesulfame potassium or its combination with aspartame, suggesting a compensatory antioxidant response to mild oxidative challenges. A similar study by Bekheet (2020) reported increased antioxidant responses in rats exposed to artificial sweeteners. Contrastingly, sucrose showed no adverse effect on oxidative stress markers, reinforcing its safety as a metabolic substrate.

CONCLUSION

The combination of acesulfame potassium and aspartame negatively affected reproductive hormones and liver enzyme profiles, suggesting their potential to disrupt metabolic and endocrine functions. Individually, acesulfame potassium showed more pronounced effects on hormonal levels than aspartame, emphasizing the synergistic toxicity of the combination. Sucrose, on the other hand, exhibited a neutral or beneficial effect, with no significant alterations in hormonal or biochemical parameters. Therefore, there is a need for caution in consuming artificial sweetener combinations, and calls for further studies to elucidate their long-term effects on health.

Conflict of interest

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interest to disclose

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